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Innovation Challenge for 'New Idea/ Suggestion to improve the working of Indian Railways'

Abstract: The development of any nation is governed by the infrastructure and transportation industry. The major hindrances for such kind of projects are land acquisition. So in our project the proposal is of elevated transport industry supported by piers, columns and beams like flyovers. Imagine a flyover passing across the nation, which will provide all the basic services of transportation and utilities of daily use.

Since the cost of such project will be very high hence we are proposing multi use corridors. When entire project is considered together then the overall project cost will be much less. The maintenance of the utilities will be much easier and safe. The interference of the dwellers can be totally eliminated which will reduce the accidents and will decrease the transportation time. The overall profit will be multi folds and the land can also be utilized for other purpose.

In India different ministries receive the funds and execute the project independently. This type of working leads to wastage of a lot of resources as well as funds. Whereas we can generate inter-ministry projects and with minimum funding we can generate maximum outputs.

Explanation:

The concept is very simple all the tracks of bullet trains will be made as flyovers since at ground level the chances of accidents will be very high and will be a frequent issue. So to compensate the high cost of flyover various other modules are clubbed together to get maximum benefit from the high value infrastructure development.

The bursting population of INDIA is already a concern but in near future land will be a scarce commodity and it will be prime hurdle for any mega project. And at the same time in the name of development we are losing our agricultural lands and forest lands. So every step should be taken to conserve land and green belts. This project will ensure that once the project is completed the forest reserves are intact and the habitat is also not disturbed any more, only a few pillars at regular intervals will be made in comparison to disturbance caused by railway, roads and the infrastructure development which keeps on growing along them.

The best part will be the same land will be used as road for express way, tracks for bullet trains, transmission lines, water/ waste water management network, Oil distribution network, Solar power plants, wind turbines to trap the energy from the bullet trains and seasonal winds, rain water harvesting canal, and in addition all this the land is still free for agriculture or any other organic development.

We are clubbing the following disciplines to execute this mega project:

1. National highways/ Road ways
2. Railways – Bullet trains
3. Water supply
4. Waste water disposal
5. Power Industry Renewal energy
 - a. Solar power
 - b. Wind energy
 - c. Biogas plant
6. Oil and gas industry
7. Power grid
8. Rain water harvesting

In this manner we will get funding from all these respective ministries. But we will save in cost for the most expansive items like:

1. Land
2. Independent infrastructure not required
3. Independent energy source not required
4. Continuous supply of fuel not required
5. Instead these infrastructures are actually are cash rewards with largest solar power plant, wind power plant, bio gas power plant, power distribution network, freight charges, fertilizers, nutrient rich and many more.
6. The pipelines buried underground are difficult to maintain and trace the faults. This project will have cheaper maintenance cost.

7. Damage to road due to harsh weather, may it be summer or rainy season. If the roads are covered. Then its life will be more hence huge saving in terms of maintenance

Feasibility/Viability of seamless Implementation of the proposed idea/ suggestion in existing setup, explained –

This project is very much feasible since it has all the answers to roadblocks to any mega project may it be:

1. Land - The land of road transport or railway can be utilized for the project.
2. Fund – Since multiple ministries are involved hence none of them will be over burdened for cash flow or funding.
3. Maintenance – All the utilities are visible hence it will be much easy to attend any fault.
4. Environmental – Since very limited green belt will be disturbed and the same can be easily relocated hence environmentally it is very supportive project.
5. Social - Any area it crosses will get connected with a reliable power grid hence will be of high interest to everyone without compromising their personal interest of land, etc.

Elaboration of stage-wise migration plan of the proposed idea/ suggestion with uninterrupted operation –

Since this is an independent project hence it can be made along the tracks without any interference to the existing systems.

Originality of the proposed idea/ suggestion explaining how the proposed idea/suggestion is an original idea/suggestion:

This idea is by product of continuously exploring the hurdles of bullet trains and finding its solution. Finally a combination of modules is established which will produce maximum profit out of the proposed project.

Possible constraints anticipated in deployment to be explained – SWOT Analysis

STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It will reduce the overall transportation time of the nation. 2. Can have first solar power operated bullet train of the world. 3. Multiple uses of land resources and still land will be free for any additional use. 4. Further hanging type train can also be provided below each slab for local transportation and bullet train will be used only for long distance. 5. This project alone has the potential to boom Indian economy. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This is a mega project hence will require a lot of time. 2. Specialized and advance construction machines and expertise will be required. 3. Aligning all the ministries for common interest will be a big challenge.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Huge employment opportunities 2. Huge amount of green power will be generated. 3. This project will help in connecting all the remote areas to get the best services such as power, clean drinking/service water, sewerage network, connectivity with cities and many more. 4. Say not to the wastage of land in making roads and railways. Soil should be utilized for green forest belts and agriculture. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If the project is not designed with field experts and with the latest techniques then the project can also cause huge wastage of resources. 2. Clash of interest of various ministries and departments.

Typical section indicating all the utilities and services

**Typical plan and elevation for green energy potential of trains
(By wind and air displaced by trains)**

